

KEY INDICATORS

After a sharp increase in the organic farmland area in 2021, with 803,958 hectares, Portugal reached rank six in the EU in 2024. In terms of organic area share, it achieved 20.3%, thus coming very close to the 2030 EU target of 25%. Growth from 2001-2024 was more than tenfold and thus considerably higher than in many other EU countries. Retail sales data is not available for Portugal.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

73,504 ha (1.9%)

803,958 ha (20.3%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

933.9%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

26,327 ha (2.1%)

192,650 ha (18.4%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

26,910 ha (3.3%)

184,292 ha (21.3%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

20,266 ha (1.4%)

428.016 ha (20.2%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

983 (0.2%)

15,989 (5.5%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

10

Processors

17

1,226

Importers

N/D

84

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Imports

N/D

5,649 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN PORTUGAL

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat, Mediterranean Organic Agriculture Network, Ministry of Agriculture, Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

Portugal's CAP Strategic Plan foresees growth of almost 250% compared with 2018, building on the sharp increase in certified area in 2021 (see above). The budgeted increase in expenditure does not quite keep up with this, with average expenditure per hectare forecast to fall by 13%. For most crop types, payments have been increased slightly, but the payments for grassland have been reduced substantially for producers with lower stocking rates. For most crops, conversion payments were 20% higher in 2019, but the difference has been reduced to 5-10% from 2023. The organic support scheme was closed to new entrants from 2025, although it may reopen for young farmers in 2026. It is scheduled to reopen in 2027.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	206 kha	689 kha (+235%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	5.7 %	19.2% (+237%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	96%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	25 M€	74 M€ (+192%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	124 €	108 € (-13%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1)*	395 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	874 M€	29.1%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	484 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	6,620 M€	6%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019 ³	P2	204	96/456 ¹	600	900	618	300/643 ¹
	2023 ³	P1/P2	102+50/LU ²	98/475 ¹	640	910/975 ¹	630	320/656 ¹
Change from 2019 to 2023			To -50%	+2/4% ¹	+7%	+9/3% ¹	+2%	+7/2% ¹
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019 ³	P2	170	80/380 ¹	600	760/900 ¹	515	250/536 ¹
	2023 ³	P2	97+49/LU ²	89/430 ¹	610	825/927 ¹	570	290/600 ¹
Change from 2019 to 2023			To -43%	+11/13% ¹	+2%	+9/3% ¹	+11%	+16/12% ¹
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+20%	+20%	0%	+20/0% ¹	+20%	+20%
	2023		+5%	+10%	+5%	+10/5% ¹	+10%	+10%

¹higher per ha values for irrigated crops / ²LU = livestock unit / ³Degressive payments 100% values shown, payments reduced to 80%, 50% or 20% of values shown for additional areas, area bands vary between crops

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing - P2 funding use in Madeira

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Portugal's current national OAP is also its first. Unlike many other action plans, the rapid increase in organic area in 2021/22 meant that the 2027 target set has been exceeded. This is also true for the 19.2% target set in the CAP Strategic Plan. Like other action plans, the focus is on market development and information initiatives, but there are some references to capacity building including the establishment of an organic production centre and market observatory.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	2017-27	12% of UAA by 2027 ¹	50% more consumption

¹already exceeded in 2022 (see above)

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2017-2027)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Portugal is negligible. Portugal was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. The national OAP highlights reduction of regulatory constraints for organic aquaculture. As funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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Design
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Publication year
2026

